

Review Future trends in the design of sustainable, Eco-friendly pesticides and the impact of chemical pesticides on the environment

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Abstract- Bio pesticides are pest control products derived from natural sources, such as microbes, microorganisms (insects and pathogens), plant extracts, and certain minerals. Many bio pesticides are considered environmentally safe and can complement or substitute conventional chemical pesticides. The topic of pollution has drawn the attention of researchers and specialists from various disciplines, whether scientific or human. Physicists, chemists, health, environmental and geographic scientists have been interested in it. However, the interest of chemists came recently despite their close connection to the topic of pollution. Chemistry is a science concerned with studying the relationships between natural and human phenomena. **Research objective:** To understand chemical pesticides, their history of manufacture, and their benefits, to study the risks caused by chemical pesticides and to clarify the phenomenon of environmental pollution caused by pesticides, which are sometimes used randomly, without proper scientific oversight. As we enter the twenty-first century, we must reconsider many aspects of our lives in order to protect future generations and live in a clean, pollution-free environment. Future trends in the design of sustainable, Eco-friendly pesticides and finally, advancements in application techniques, as well as future research directions.

Keywords: Eco-friendly, Chemical Pesticides, Future Trends, Pesticide Design.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chemicals are an integral part of our lives, assisting us in many activities, protecting us from and controlling many diseases, and contributing to increased agricultural productivity.[1] Their benefits are countless, but on the other hand, they can pose a threat to our health and poison our environment.[2] Inappropriate release of chemicals into the environment can turn them into pollutants in the air we breathe, the water we drink, and the food we eat. [3] They can also affect rivers, lakes, and forests, harming water and soil, changing the climate, and disrupting ecosystems. We are all

exposed to toxic chemicals. [4] Whether a chemical can harm us depends on its quantity, duration, and frequency of exposure, as well as its toxicity and individual sensitivity. [5] The amount may be very small, but it accumulates in the body over long periods of time. Some chemicals cause harm several years after exposure. [6] Although the intensity of exposure may be brief, exposure can be repeated and at excessive concentrations. Children, the elderly, pregnant women, and those with underlying health conditions are more susceptible than healthy adults. [7, 8] Chemical industry growth in both developing and developed countries is expected to accelerate in the next century. [9] Chemical safety, which means managing chemical hazards, is essential if growth is to be beneficial and

not cause catastrophic damage to humans and the environment. [10] A novel feature of this review is that Future trends in the design of sustainable, Eco-friendly pesticides. Are receiving increasing attention in contemporary agriculture due to their eco-friendly properties and minimal risks to human health. This paper presents efforts, along with innovations from the private sector, are driving the development of novel formulations and approaches aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of these biological agents.

II. HISTORY OF PESTICIDES

In the past, people protected their crops from insects and pests using chemicals. [11] The Sumerians used elemental sulfur to protect their crops. In the middle Ages, farmers used substances such as arsenic and lead to protect crops. [12, 13] While in China, arsenic and mercury compounds were used to combat body lice and other pests, the Greeks and Romans, meanwhile, used oil, ash, and sulfur to protect themselves, their livestock, and their crops from various types of pests. [14]. By the 19th century, researchers began focusing more on natural pest control techniques involving compounds derived from tropical plant roots and chrysanthemums. [15] In 1939, dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) was discovered. It proved to be highly effective and was rapidly adopted worldwide as an insecticide. However, twenty years later, due to its biological effects and human health concerns, DDT was banned in nearly 86 countries [16, 17]. Throughout history, chemical pesticides have attracted significant attention from scientists. Agricultural advancements played a key role in the development of modern pesticides, marking a pivotal point in pest control strategies. [18] The use of modern pesticides has greatly contributed to improving agricultural productivity. This raises questions such as: What is the historical development of pesticides? What are the different types of pesticides, both ancient and modern? And what are their impacts on the environment and human health?

Phase I: Ancient Types of Pesticides

The early development of chemical pesticides was based on the use of plants and basic elements or compounds. Subsequent scientific and cultural advancements led to the discovery and application of additional pest control agents. [19]

1. Sulfur

Sulfur was among the first documented chemical compounds used as pesticides in history. Lime sulfur solutions were historically employed to eliminate lice infestations. Later, sulfur dioxide produced by burning elemental sulfur was used to suffocate insects and other small pests by interfering with their respiration. When applied as a liquid or powder, sulfuric solutions inhibited insect growth. Even today, sulfur remains widely used in modern pest management as a fungicide and insect deterrent. [20]

2. Heavy Metals

Heavy metal compounds were likely used initially due to their high toxicity. For instance, arsenic-based compounds are highly toxic to insects, bacteria, and fungi. Arsenic is still used today in wood preservation and some agricultural pest control practices. [21] The main advantage of these inorganic pesticides at the time was their persistence they did not degrade easily. However, this also led to their accumulation in ecosystems; it poses significant health risks to humans, leading to environmental destruction. [22]

3. Chemical Pesticides

Pesticides are chemicals used to kill or control agricultural pests. In general, a pesticide refers to a chemical or biological agent such as viruses, bacteria, antimicrobials, or disinfectants that repels, inhibits, or exterminates pests. [23] The use of pesticides has become so widespread that the term is often used synonymously with plant protection products. Pesticides typically eliminate insects or control various agricultural pests that can harm crops or livestock, thereby reducing farm productivity. The most common categories include: [24, 25 and 26]

- Insecticides, targeting insects
 - Herbicides, targeting weeds
 - Rodenticides, targeting rodents
 - Fungicides, used to control fungi and molds
- According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), pesticides refer to chemical agents or combinations of substances specifically designed to inhibit, eliminate, or manage pests. These pests may include organisms that transmit diseases to humans or animals, as well as invasive plant or animal species that negatively impact the cultivation, handling, preservation, transportation, or commercialization of food products, agricultural goods, timber and its derivatives, or livestock feed. The term also includes substances intended to be administered to animals to control insects, arachnids, or other pests in or on their bodies. [27]
- Chemical pesticides are substances used either alone or in combination with other materials for the purpose of exterminating, repelling, or mitigating the harm caused by targeted pests. Pests are defined as living organisms that cause harm to humans, their products, or their property. [28] They include a wide range of organisms such as insects, mites, fungi, bacteria, viruses, weeds, parasites, scorpions, rodents, snails, and predatory birds. [29]
- Pesticides are classified according to several criteria, the most important of which is the type of pest they are intended to control. [30] Examples include insecticides, acaricides, and fungicides. An effective chemical pesticide should:
- Demonstrate efficacy at a specified concentration,
 - Be economically viable
 - Cause no significant harm to biotic or abiotic components of the ecosystem
 - Leave no toxic residues on or in food products. [31]

IV. BENEFITS OF CHEMICAL PESTICIDES

The primary benefits of pesticides are the direct advantages derived from their effects. For example, eliminating larvae that feed on crops results in higher yields and improved quality, such as in the case of cabbage. These primary effects lead to a total of 26 key benefits ranging from recreational lawn protection to saving human lives. [32]

Secondary benefits are those that are less immediate or less visible. They may be subtle, indirect, or long-term, making it harder to establish direct cause-effect relationships. However, these secondary effects can still serve as strong justifications for pesticide use. [33] For instance, increased cabbage yields may result in additional income, which could then be allocated to children's education or healthcare ultimately contributing to a healthier and more educated population. Several secondary benefits have been identified, ranging from personal well-being to biodiversity preservation. [34]

Pesticides are extensively applied in both agricultural and horticultural practices to protect crops and safeguard human health by targeting harmful pests. While they play a crucial role in boosting food production and minimizing the economic damage caused by pest infestations, their extensive usage has raised considerable concerns. [36]

Phase II: Types of pesticides and their toxic effects on humans:

The following illustrates the types of pesticides and their toxic effects on humans.

1. Insecticides

The application of pesticides enhances agricultural productivity by suppressing disease-causing microorganisms, thereby promoting greater availability and consumption of fresh fruits and vegetables. Pesticides are generally classified into four main categories: organochlorines, carbamates, organophosphates, and pyrethroids, as depicted in Figure 1 along with their respective chemical structures.

Figure 1. Classification of pesticides with chemical structure.

A- Organ chlorine insecticides

Shown Fig. 2 They is in the form of a powder that is insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents and oils. [37,38] Therefore, they are stored in the fatty tissues of the body, causing toxicity and affecting the nerve centers in the spinal cord and the nerve centers in the cerebral cortex. Examples of these include: [39]

Figure 2: Examples of Organ chlorine insecticides.

B- Phosphorus insecticides

This group includes a large number of known compounds, the most common of which are the following: Shown Fig. 3 parathion and dip Terex [40]

Figure 1: Examples of Phosphorus insecticides.

C- Carbonate insecticides

The compounds in this group have properties similar to organ phosphorus compounds. They are liquids, some of which have an oily consistency and an unpleasant odor, and some of which dissolve in water and organic solvents. They are used as

pesticides for agricultural pests and insect pests such as Shown Fig. 4. [41]

Figure 4: Examples of Carbonate insecticides.

D- Pyrethroids insecticides

Synthetic pyrethroids, illustrated in Figure 5, are chemically modified derivatives of natural pyrethrins extracted from the *Chrysanthemum cinerariae folium* plant. These compounds consist of esters formed from chrysanthemum acid (ethyl 2,2-dimethyl-3-(1-isobutenyl)cyclopropane-1-carboxylate) and halogenated variants of related acids and alcohols. Due to the rapid photo degradation of the natural constituents found in *C. cinerariaefolium* extracts when exposed to light, these natural compounds were replaced by synthetic alternatives, which were initially regarded as safe for humans and higher-order animals. [43]

Figure 5: Examples of Pyrethroids insecticides.

I. Fungicides

These pesticides are used to protect plants from fungal infection, eliminate fungi, or limit their activity if the plant is infected. They are mineral or organic compounds, such as copper compounds, sulfur, organometallic mercury, etc. Dinitrophenol compounds are widely used as insecticides and

fungicides, as well as to eliminate ticks that infect livestock. Examples include Shown Fig.6: [44]

Figure 6: Examples of Fungicides pesticides.

II. Herbicides

Some compounds in this group have the ability to eliminate a specific, limited type of weed that infests crops, while others have the ability to eliminate all plants and weeds. These are commonly used to clear streets and agricultural roads of vegetation, as well as to clean railway lines and other uses, the most important of which is the use of 2,4-Dinitro-Ortho-Cresol Shown Fig.7. [45]

Figure 7: Shown 2, 4, Dinitro-Ortho-Cresol pesticides.

III. PESTICIDES CONTAINING ARSENIC

Arsenic compounds have been known since ancient times and have many uses. Some of these compounds are still used to control ants, fungi, weeds, mice, and rats. They are also used in the manufacture of dyes, ceramics, and other materials. Arsenic trioxide is used to spread these inorganic pesticides, as is copper arsenate Shown Fig.8, also known as Paris green. [46]

Figure 8: Shown Pesticides containing arsenic.

III: Treatment techniques

The fate of pesticides is not limited to the site of application. Thus, can contaminate several ecosystems, both terrestrial and aquatic. Due to the complexity of the contaminant, the removal of agrochemicals from water and soil is still challenging for specialists. [47] Various techniques have been used to remove pesticides. Traditional water treatment techniques, such as adsorption and filtration, offer effective alternatives for remediating contaminated water systems. Among these, adsorption has emerged as a particularly promising method for eliminating pesticide residues from aquatic environments. The adsorption process of agrochemicals is governed by various interaction mechanisms, including electrostatic attraction, hydrophobic interactions, pore-filling effects, hydrogen bonding, and π - π stacking. These mechanisms, illustrated in Figure 9, demonstrate the ways in which adsorbent materials contribute to the efficient removal of pesticides. [48, 49]

IV. CONCLUSION

Figure 9: Some reaction mechanisms in an adsorbent for pesticide removal.

Phase IV: Sustainable pesticide designs Key Future Trends

Sustainable pesticide designs are moving toward the use of innovative technologies and environmentally safe formulations, with an emphasis on minimizing harm to non-target organisms. [50] This includes the use of bio pesticides, nanotechnology, and targeted delivery techniques, as well as the integration of integrated pest management, precision agriculture, and organic farming. [51] Bio pesticides: The use of microorganisms (such as bacteria and fungi) or their byproducts to produce natural pesticides with minimal environmental impact. Nanotechnology: [52] The development of nanoparticles to encapsulate or transport pesticides, increasing their effectiveness and reducing the amount of pesticide used. Targeted delivery techniques: [53] Designing pesticides that reach only the target pest, minimizing their impact on non-target organisms and the environment. [54] Integrating a range of pest control strategies, including biological control, crop rotation, the use of traps, and good agricultural practices, to reduce reliance on chemical pesticides. [55] Using modern technology for precision agriculture, which allows pesticides to be applied selectively, at the right time, and in precise quantities. Organic agriculture: [56] Using natural agricultural methods to produce crops, reducing reliance on chemical pesticides. Low-toxicity pesticides: Developing pesticides with less toxicity to non-target organisms and the environment. [57]

Microbial bio pesticides are receiving increasing attention in contemporary agriculture due to their eco-friendly properties and minimal risks to human health. Ongoing research efforts, along with innovations from the private sector, are driving the development of novel formulations and approaches aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of these biological agents. Key emerging directions in bio pesticide research include the use of microbial agents, botanical extracts and essential oils, RNA-based bio pesticides, nanotechnology applications, and synergistic combinations of multiple bio pesticide types to achieve more effective pest management. As the global shift toward sustainable and environmentally responsible pest control accelerates, bio pesticides have seen remarkable progress.

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